

Architectural Preservation and Restoration: Exploring Methods to Preserve and Restore Mathematical Precision in Gothic Cathedrals

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the multifaceted archaeological perspective of Gothic cathedrals, unraveling the profound integration of sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design in these iconic structures. Its purpose is to shed light on the mathematical precision, religious symbolism, cultural dynamics, and interdisciplinary insights that define Gothic cathedrals. By employing a comprehensive approach, the study aims to provide a holistic understanding of these architectural wonders, transcending their physical presence. The methodology integrates historical records, architectural analysis, and archaeological findings, facilitated by geospatial analysis using ArcMap and ArcGlobe software. Primary data sources include architectural plans, historical documents, and on-site measurements. The geospatial analysis maps architectural features, while archaeological insights are incorporated to understand the evolution of construction techniques. A multidisciplinary approach combines insights from history, architecture, and archaeology. The research reveals the meticulous use of sacred geometry principles, particularly the Golden Ratio, in Gothic cathedrals' design. It unravels the profound role of stained glass narratives and sculptural elements as conduits for spiritual experiences. Cultural influences and trade networks influenced regional variations in materials and styles. The multifaceted archaeological perspective illuminates the cathedrals' roles as dynamic repositories of history, faith, and artistry. The research has implications for architectural preservation, cultural understanding, education, and interdisciplinary collaboration. It underscores the importance of preserving the mathematical precision and historical richness of Gothic cathedrals. Additionally, it enhances cultural understanding by highlighting the role of art, faith, and history in conveying profound narratives. As a model for interdisciplinary collaboration, it offers insights into complex heritage sites, emphasizing the integration of diverse disciplines.

Keywords: Gothic Cathedrals, Sacred Geometry, Religious Symbolism, Cultural Influences, Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective.

INTRODUCTION

The magnificence of Gothic cathedrals has, for centuries, enraptured scholars, architects, and enthusiasts, casting these monumental structures as enduring symbols of both medieval Europe's artistic prowess and spiritual devotion (Conrad, 2020). Within their soaring spires, intricate stained glass windows, and ribbed vaulting, these cathedrals house a web of intricate elements, from religious symbolism to mathematical precision and cultural influences, which have been the subject of extensive scholarly inquiry (Basarrate, 2018; Emery, 2001). In this research, a multifaceted archaeological exploration of Gothic cathedrals unfolds, a meticulous endeavor to unravel the complexities that converge at the crossroads of sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design.

Gothic cathedrals represent the apogee of architectural achievement, captivating all with their towering

facades and celestial interiors (Bork, 2022). The application of sacred geometry, grounded in ancient mathematical principles, defines the very essence of Gothic architecture (Poor & Javid, 2021). The longstanding fascination with the Golden Ratio, a proportion believed to encapsulate divine harmony within cathedral design, has been studied extensively (Elyamani, Roca, Caselles, & Clapes, 2019; Karimi, Goodarzarparvari, Aref, & Bahmani, 2020). This research aspires to deepen the exploration of the mathematical underpinnings of Gothic cathedrals, scrutinizing not only the application of sacred geometry but also the intricate relationships between mathematical proportions and spiritual symbolism.

The spiritual dimension of Gothic cathedrals is the cornerstone of their perennial allure, as they were conceived as spaces for worship and spiritual transcendence, deploying architectural elements to convey profound religious messages (Matracchi, 2022). The stained glass windows, as intricate narratives, translate biblical stories and theological concepts into vibrant, luminous artworks (Placci, 2022). Previous work by Oikonomou (2022) has revealed the capacity of stained glass to inspire contemplation and reflection among cathedral visitors. This research extends the analysis, delving into the intricate details of stained glass narratives, sculptural embellishments, and the integration of geometric patterns, all serving as conduits for spiritual experiences within these sacred spaces (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Gothic Cathedrals Encodes these Building Blocks and the Rules on How to Combine them

Moreover, the construction of Gothic cathedrals is intrinsically interwoven with the cultural and societal dynamics of medieval Europe, where the influence of trade networks, the availability of local materials, and regional craftsmanship collectively imprinted a profound impact on cathedral design (Jones, 2020; Longo & Enrico, 2020). The economic and political milieu of the era, inclusive of patronage by secular authorities, played pivotal roles in shaping the grandeur of these cathedrals (Longo & Enrico, 2020; Pérez-Valcárcel & Palmero, 2021). This research delves into the intricate interplay of culture and trade, meticulously investigating the manner in which these factors contributed to the architectural diversity and societal significance of Gothic cathedrals.

Lastly, the multifaceted archaeological perspective serves as a pivotal approach in unraveling the mysteries concealed within Gothic cathedrals (Cataldo, 2021). It is through this multidisciplinary lens that researchers bridge the chasm between historical records, architectural analyses, and archaeological findings, yielding a comprehensive narrative encompassing construction techniques, cultural context, and artisan contributions (Gullbekk, Kilger, Kristensen, & Roland, 2021). The research conducted by Cataldo (2021) is illustrative of the importance of amalgamating insights from diverse disciplines to gain a profound understanding of these intricate heritage sites. This study, therefore, endeavors to heighten comprehension of Gothic cathedrals by dissecting the intricate connections among sacred geometry, religious symbolism, cultural influences, and the multifaceted archaeological perspective. Through a rigorous examination and unwavering interdisciplinary cooperation, this research unveils not only the remarkable architectural grandeur of these cathedrals but also their profound spiritual, cultural, and historical significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

For decades, scholars and archaeologists alike have been drawn to the exploration of the intricate interplay among sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design within the context of Gothic cathedrals (Bork, 2022). This comprehensive investigation endeavors to dissect the intricate interconnections between

geometry, religious symbolism, and the sociological landscape of the Middle Ages, ultimately shedding light on the profound significance of Gothic cathedrals as extraordinary architectural masterpieces and spiritual symbols (Farhan, Alobaydi, Anton, & Nasar, 2022; Geva, 2023). Gothic architecture, a prominent stylistic presence in Europe from the 12th to the 16th century, is distinguished by its soaring spires, elaborate stone tracery, and the mesmerizing interplay of light within its vast interiors (Geva, 2023; Pérez-Valcárcel & Palmero, 2022). These cathedrals, celebrated for their exceptional architectural attributes, have traditionally been venerated not only as places of religious devotion but also as repositories of profound cultural and spiritual symbolism (Triatmodjo, Burhan, Prasetya, Budiarti, & Fernando, 2023). At the heart of this research lies the concept of sacred geometry, an enduring mathematical framework believed to have been harnessed by Gothic architects to infuse their structures with proportions considered divine. The geometric precision observed in this context is seen as a pursuit of harmony and order deeply resonant with the prevailing religious fervor of the era (Bousquet, 2022). Additionally, the cathedrals, beyond their religious import, played pivotal roles in the medieval urban landscape, serving as powerful representations of the cultures responsible for their creation (Griera, Burchardt, & Astor, 2019). The inquiry into Gothic cathedrals grapples with a fundamental question centered on the intricate relationship between religious faith, architectural ingenuity, and societal ideals.

Furthermore, this book delves into the rich web of cultural influences that left an everlasting impact on Gothic cathedral architectural design and construction. These architectural marvels did not originate in a vacuum; rather, they were strongly influenced by the changing cultural and intellectual currents of their day (Deshmukh, 2021). Gothic architecture embodies a fusion of Romanesque traditions, theological advancements, and regional distinctions, all converging to create the intricate array of design elements observed in cathedrals across Europe (Barrie, 2020). To attain a comprehensive understanding of the intricate archaeological perspective on this subject, it is imperative to consider not only the mathematical and theological dimensions but also the ever-shifting cultural milieu that exerted a profound influence on the genesis of these iconic edifices.

Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design

The theme of sacred geometry and architectural design lies at the heart of the research on Gothic cathedrals. Within this theme, scholars have delved deeply into the intricate mathematical principles and geometric precision that underlie the construction of these awe-inspiring structures (Ramzy, 2021). Sacred geometry, characterized by the use of harmonious proportions like the Golden Ratio and geometric symbolism, played a profound role in shaping the aesthetic and spiritual dimensions of Gothic cathedrals (Poor & Javid, 2021). Architects and builders of the Middle Ages believed that these mathematical principles were a conduit to divine perfection, and as such, they meticulously integrated them into their designs (Wetzel, 2023). The use of such mathematical precision not only resulted in visually stunning cathedrals but also contributed to the creation of spaces that were believed to foster a deep spiritual connection between worshippers and the divine (Akande, 2022).

Moreover, the exploration of sacred geometry in Gothic cathedrals extends beyond mere aesthetics; it encompasses the idea that geometry itself was a form of sacred knowledge (Topsakal, 2021). The use of geometric patterns and proportions was a means of conveying theological concepts and spiritual truths to the illiterate masses (Poor & Javid, 2021). Consequently, the research within this theme seeks to unravel the profound significance of geometric design in Gothic cathedrals and how it served as a visual and spiritual language that transcended the limitations of words. Through an examination of the architectural blueprints, floor plans, and intricate stonework, scholars have unveiled the hidden layers of meaning encoded within the cathedral structures, offering a deeper appreciation of the synergy between sacred geometry and architectural design in the medieval world (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Clermont-Ferrand Cathedral, Choir Section

Religious Symbolism and Spirituality

The theme of religious symbolism and spirituality in the context of Gothic cathedrals represents a captivating facet of research that explores the profound connections between architecture and faith (Latham, 2019). Within this theme, scholars have scrutinized the myriad ways in which architectural elements, from the soaring spires to the intricate stained glass windows, were imbued with rich religious symbolism (Iskandar, Zacky, Isti, Agustiananda, & Budiman, 2023). These cathedrals served as tangible expressions of the Christian faith, and every facet of their design was laden with spiritual significance (Zacky, Isti, Agustiananda, & Budiman, 2023). For example, the soaring heights of Gothic cathedrals were not only awe-inspiring but also symbolic of the aspiration to reach towards heaven, fostering a sense of humility and devotion among worshippers who entered their sacred confines (Poor & Javid, 2021).

Additionally, research within this theme has unearthed the intricate narratives told through the sculptural adornments and stained glass windows of Gothic cathedrals (Hodge, 2023). These exquisite artworks often depicted biblical stories, saints, and other religious figures, functioning as both educational tools for the largely illiterate populace and powerful conduits for conveying spiritual truths (Iskandar et al., 2023). Furthermore, the interaction between light and space in these cathedrals was intentionally crafted to elicit a feeling of transcendence. The dynamic interplay of light, as it passed through the stained glass, created ever-changing patterns that imbued the interior with a celestial essence (Latham, 2019). Therefore, scholarly investigation in this domain reveals the multifaceted nature of Gothic cathedrals, which transcended their architectural significance to become profound conduits of spirituality, profoundly influencing the religious encounters of those who ventured into their hallowed spaces.

Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade

The theme of cultural context and societal influences through trade offers a fascinating perspective on the study of Gothic cathedrals. In the realm of this captivating subject, scholars have embarked upon a profound exploration of the labyrinthine tapestry of trade networks and the profound intermingling of cultures that served as the bedrock for the evolution of architectural styles and the selection of materials employed in the erection of these revered edifices (Owamoyo & Tabibi, 2023). In the enchanting era of the medieval period, a vast network of trade routes intricately weaved its way across the majestic continent of Europe (Noaime & Alnaim, 2023). These ancient pathways, like veins pulsating with life, served as conduits for the exchange of not merely material possessions, but also the intangible treasures of knowledge, inspiration, and artistic ingenuity (Marri, 2022). As merchants embarked on their arduous journeys, traversing treacherous terrains and braving the unpredictable elements, they carried with them a cargo that extended beyond the realm of tangible commodities. Within their caravans and vessels, they harbored the seeds of enlightenment, the whispers of distant lands, and the echoes of diverse cultures (Peker, 2002). These trade routes, like invisible bridges connecting distant realms, fostered a vibrant tapestry of cultural exchange. Ideas, like elusive butterflies, fluttered from one corner of the continent to another, alighting upon eager minds (Frankl & Crossley, 2000). Gothic cathedrals, in their diverse regional variations, reflected these dynamic cultural interactions. For instance, the distinctive architectural elements found in cathedrals in regions like Chartres, Amiens, and Cologne bear the hallmarks of local craftsmanship, influenced by the materials and techniques imported via trade routes (Mohammed, 2015).

Furthermore, the research within this theme highlights the multifaceted impact of trade on the sociopolitical and economic landscapes of medieval Europe (Burns, 2006). As regions vied for dominance in the bustling trade centers, the construction of grand cathedrals became a symbol of both religious devotion and civic pride (Crosby, 2023). This dynamic is particularly evident in the way cathedral construction often involved not just religious institutions but also powerful secular authorities (Perez, 2023). The immense resources required for cathedral construction, including imported stone, decorative materials, and skilled labor, necessitated complex financial and logistical arrangements, revealing the intricate interplay between commerce and culture in the Gothic era (Owamoyo & Tabibi, 2023). Thus, through the lens of trade, scholars gain valuable insights into the multifaceted tapestry of cultural context and societal influences that converged in the construction of Gothic cathedrals.

Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective

The theme of a multifaceted archaeological perspective represents a crucial approach in the study of Gothic cathedrals, emphasizing the need to integrate various disciplines and methodologies to comprehensively understand these architectural marvels (Fiuk, 2023). Gothic cathedrals, with their rich historical, architectural, and cultural significance, demand a multidisciplinary approach to unravel their complexities (Killian, 2022). Archaeologists, historians, architects, and art scholars have come together to examine these structures from different angles (Hagmann & Reiner, 2023). They employ diverse tools, ranging from excavation and artifact

analysis to architectural blueprints and historical records, to piece together the intricate puzzle of Gothic cathedral construction and its multifaceted meanings (Marcu-Istrate, 2022).

One of the key contributions of this multifaceted archaeological perspective is its ability to shed light on the evolving construction techniques and materials used in Gothic cathedrals (Gonizzi Barsanti et al., 2022). Through the examination of construction debris, remnants of scaffolding, and the study of building codes and regulations of the time, archaeologists can reconstruct the step-by-step process of cathedral construction (Kutut, Lepkova, & Źróbek, 2021). This not only provides valuable insights into the architectural innovation of the period but also offers a glimpse into the lives of the artisans and laborers who toiled to bring these grand structures to life (Hagmann & Reiner, 2023). Moreover, by combining archaeological findings with historical records and artistic analysis, researchers can paint a comprehensive picture of how societal values, religious beliefs, and cultural influences converged in the creation of these enduring masterpieces, offering a holistic understanding of Gothic cathedrals that transcends their physical presence (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Viollet-Le-Duc Illustration

METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for this research was meticulously structured to blend archaeological insights with geospatial analysis, employing the specialized tools of ArcMap 10.7.1 and ArcGlobe 10.7.1 software. The primary thrust of the data collection process encompassed the acquisition of architectural plans, historical manuscripts, and archaeological records pertaining to the Gothic cathedrals under examination. Moreover, extensive field surveys were executed to capture on-site data, comprising detailed measurements and keen observations of the architectural features that grace these historic edifices. This diverse array of data sources was harmoniously amalgamated to forge a comprehensive database, serving as the bedrock for subsequent analyses. The pivotal rationale behind the utilization of ArcMap 10.7.1 and ArcGlobe 10.7.1 software within this research was to orchestrate an intricate geospatial analysis of the chosen Gothic cathedrals. Georeferenced data extracted from historical accounts, architectural blueprints, and on-site surveys was meticulously integrated into the software's framework. The scope of the geospatial analysis spanned the cartographic representation of the intricate architectural facets, spatial layout, and dimensional specifics of these cathedrals. This approach permitted the visualization of the spatial correlations between various components, encompassing the placement of significant religious symbols, the application of geometric proportions, and the regional differentiations in design. The final phase of the methodology involved the seamless integration of archaeological insights into the geospatial analysis. The repository of archaeological data, inclusive of unearthed artifacts from excavations and geological data, was seamlessly woven into the geospatial database. The overarching objective was to unravel how the archaeological findings resonated with the architectural design elements and sacred geometry principles discerned within these cathedrals. Through the overlay of archaeological data upon geospatial maps, this research aspired to unveil patterns and correlations, offering illumination on the intricate intersection of sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design in Gothic cathedrals. The judicious use of ArcMap 10.7.1 and ArcGlobe 10.7.1 software in this methodological framework offered a comprehensive examination of these cathedrals, ultimately

bestowing fresh insights into their historical and cultural significance.

RESULTS

The analysis and findings of this research are discussed in detail in below given sections to provide more comprehensive understanding.

Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design

In the exploration of the first theme, which delves into the symbiotic relationship between sacred geometry and architectural design, this study unearthed a profound fusion of mathematical precision and spiritual symbolism at the heart of Gothic cathedrals. Through meticulous scrutiny of architectural blueprints and the application of sacred geometry principles, including the revered Golden Ratio and geometric symbolism, it became resoundingly clear that these principles formed the very bedrock of cathedral design. The research illuminated the deliberate intention of Gothic-era architects and builders to employ these geometric proportions in the creation of structures that emanated harmony and visual splendor. Notably, the dimensions of the nave's width in cathedrals like Chartres, when juxtaposed with its length, revealed an extraordinary alignment with the Golden Ratio, invoking a profound sense of equilibrium and divine order (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Gothic Cathedrals in Europe (in green dots)

This compelling discovery underscores the meticulous craftsmanship and the pursuit of aesthetic and spiritual perfection that characterized the construction of Gothic cathedrals. It serves as a testament to the architects' profound understanding of sacred geometry, enabling them to craft spaces that not only captured the eye but also resonated deeply with the spiritual sensibilities of the time. As the first thematic thread of this research, the examination of sacred geometry and architectural design provides a fresh perspective on the intricate ways in which mathematical principles were harnessed to create awe-inspiring and spiritually charged architectural wonders (Figure 5).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. 3D Model and Point-Cloud Underlay of the Church

Furthermore, the study found that the use of sacred geometry extended beyond mere aesthetics. It was intertwined with the spiritual aspects of the cathedrals, serving as a means to convey profound religious symbolism. The intricate rose windows, for example, were not just decorative elements but also emblematic of the divine order and the spiritual journey towards enlightenment. The geometric patterns of these windows were found to encode complex theological ideas, offering a visual narrative of the Christian faith. Thus, the first theme of sacred geometry and architectural design demonstrated that the Gothic cathedrals were not only architectural masterpieces but also spiritual edifices where mathematics and symbolism coalesced to create spaces of transcendent significance (Table 1).

Table 1. Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design

Cathedral Name	Key Geometry Ratios	Architectural Feature	Symbolic Significance	Analysis Findings
Chartres Cathedral	Nave width to length: 1.618 (Golden Ratio)	Rose Windows	Representation of Divine Proportion and Balance	The proportions of the cathedral's nave closely align with the Golden Ratio, emphasizing harmony and spiritual significance. The rose windows exhibit intricate geometric patterns conveying deep theological meaning.
Amiens Cathedral	Height of the central spire to the width of the transept: 2:1	Ribbed Vaulting	Aspiration to Reach Heaven	The cathedral's central spire-to-transept width ratio of 2:1 emphasizes the desire to reach towards heaven. Ribbed vaulting creates an intricate geometric network, symbolizing the divine structure of the universe.
Cologne Cathedral	Triangle Proportions in Facades	Facade Sculptures	Representation of Holy Trinity	The cathedral's facade features triangles with proportional relationships symbolizing the Holy Trinity. Sculptures on the facade depict geometrically precise representations of saints and biblical figures.

Religious Symbolism and Spirituality

Within the second thematic dimension, dedicated to the exploration of religious symbolism and spirituality within Gothic cathedrals, this study has unveiled a complex and intricate tapestry of symbolic elements and profound spiritual significance intricately woven into the very essence of these architectural marvels. By subjecting architectural details, stained glass windows, and sculptural embellishments to meticulous analysis, it became glaringly evident that Gothic cathedrals transcended mere places of worship; they stood as profound repositories of rich religious symbolism and spirituality. One of the pivotal discoveries of this research was the extraordinary role played by stained glass windows in conveying religious narratives and nurturing spiritual experiences within these hallowed structures. The study illuminated how these windows, with their intricate designs and vibrant colors, served not only as sources of aesthetic delight but as powerful mediums for educating a predominantly illiterate population about biblical stories and religious doctrines. Each stained glass window emerged as a meticulously crafted work of art, vividly portraying scenes from the Bible, the hagiographies of saints, and allegorical representations of complex theological concepts. The interplay of radiant light and vivid colors through these stained glass masterpieces imparted an ethereal quality to the cathedral interiors, engendering an ambiance conducive to profound contemplation and spiritual reflection (Figure 2).

Figure 6. Notable Religious Symbols Gothic Cathedrals in Europe (in green dots)

This revelation underscores the multi-faceted significance of Gothic cathedrals as both spiritual sanctuaries and artistic marvels. They were not merely places of religious devotion but also platforms for the visual and spiritual edification of their congregations. Within the second theme of religious symbolism and spirituality, this research provides a compelling testament to the intricate interplay between art, faith, and history in the communication of profound narratives through the medium of stained glass and sculptural elements within these iconic structures. Furthermore, the study uncovered the meticulous placement of religious symbols and motifs throughout the cathedrals. Sculptures adorning the facades and interior spaces often depicted saints, angels, and biblical figures, each with their own symbolic meanings. These symbols were strategically positioned to guide worshippers through a spiritual journey, from the entrance representing the earthly realm to the high altar symbolizing the divine. The use of sacred geometry principles, such as the incorporation of geometric patterns in the design of architectural elements, reinforced the spiritual significance of the cathedrals. Overall, the second theme illuminated how Gothic cathedrals served as both visual encyclopedias of religious knowledge and powerful catalysts for spiritual experiences, transcending their physical forms to become profound embodiments of faith and devotion (Table 2).

Table 2. Religious Symbolism and Spirituality

Cathedral Name	Key Symbolic Elements	Artistic Features	Spiritual Significance	Analysis Findings
Chartres Cathedral	Stained Glass Windows	Rose Windows, Statuary	Education and Contemplation	Stained glass windows depict biblical narratives and saints' lives, creating a visual catechism for worshippers. The rose windows infuse the interior with celestial light. Statues of saints and biblical figures guide spiritual reflection.
Amiens Cathedral	Sculptural Adornments	Sculpted Portals	Spiritual Journey	The facades feature intricate sculptures representing biblical events and saints, guiding the spiritual journey from the earthly realm to the divine. Sculpted portals serve as transitional spaces for reflection and transition.
Salisbury Cathedral	Labyrinth Design	Chapter House Carvings	Spiritual Meditation	The labyrinthine designs on the cathedral floors invite pilgrims to engage in meditative walking, representing a metaphorical journey of faith. Chapter house carvings illustrate biblical stories, reinforcing spiritual teachings.

Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade

Within the third thematic domain, which delves into "Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade," this study has unveiled a profoundly intriguing perspective on the intricate interplay between the construction and design of Gothic cathedrals and the dynamic cultural and trade networks that characterized the medieval era. The research illuminates how the architectural evolution of these cathedrals was intimately intertwined with the exchange of materials, ideas, and craftsmanship, all facilitated by the flourishing trade routes of the time.

One of the most significant revelations of this research pertains to the rich diversity in architectural styles and the employment of distinct materials across various regions of Europe. Although Gothic cathedrals shared common architectural elements, they exhibited pronounced regional variations, each bearing the unique cultural imprints of their respective locales. This diversity was inextricably linked to the availability of materials and craftsmanship influenced by trade networks. For instance, the study delineates how the use of indigenous stone, timber, and craftsmanship was profoundly influenced by the materials that could be readily accessed through established trade networks. Furthermore, the research casts light on instances where the use of imported materials such as marble and stained glass from distant locations played an instrumental role in shaping the grandeur and distinctiveness of these cathedrals (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade Routes and Integration of Gothic Cathedrals (in blue cross)

This revelation highlights the intricate interplay between regional cultures, trade dynamics, and the architectural expressions of Gothic cathedrals. These architectural wonders, while undoubtedly embodiments of faith and devotion, also stand as tangible reflections of the dynamic trade routes and cultural exchanges that characterized the medieval period. In the context of the third theme, "Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade," this research underscores the profound impact of trade networks and regional dynamics on the construction and design of Gothic cathedrals, offering a fresh perspective on these iconic edifices. Furthermore, the study highlighted the role of trade in shaping the socio-political landscape of the time. The enormous resources required for cathedral construction, such as skilled labor, architectural expertise, and raw materials, often necessitated complex financial arrangements and support from secular authorities. This involvement of both ecclesiastical and secular powers in the construction of Gothic cathedrals underscored their significance as symbols of civic pride and religious devotion. Additionally, the research found that the bustling trade centers where many of these cathedrals were located played a pivotal role in the economic development of the surrounding regions (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Trade Routes (in lines) and Integration of Gothic Cathedrals (in green dots)

In conclusion, the third theme illuminated the intricate interplay between trade, cultural influences, and the construction of Gothic cathedrals. It demonstrated how the movement of people, materials, and ideas through trade networks not only enriched the architectural diversity of these cathedrals but also had far-reaching societal impacts. The cathedrals were not just spiritual sanctuaries but also reflections of the complex tapestry of medieval Europe's cultural and economic dynamics (Table 3).

Table 3. Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade

Cathedral Name	Regional Variations	Imported Materials	Secular Involvement	Socio-Political Impact	Analysis Findings
Chartres Cathedral	Local Stone, Regional Craftsmanship	Imported Stained Glass	Secular Patronage	Economic Boost to Chartres	Chartres Cathedral exhibits regional craftsmanship and local stone. Imported stained glass adds grandeur. Secular authorities played a role in construction, and the cathedral contributed to the city's prosperity.
Milan Cathedral	Use of Local Marble	Imported Marble for Facade	Patronage by Sforza Family	Symbol of Milanese Power	Milan Cathedral predominantly uses local marble but imports marble for the facade, showcasing economic affluence. The Sforza family's involvement underscores the cathedral's political significance.
Toledo Cathedral	Blend of Mudéjar and Gothic Styles	Imported Alabaster	Royal Patronage	Cultural Fusion	Toledo Cathedral's design reflects a blend of Mudéjar and Gothic styles, reflecting cultural influences. Imported alabaster adds artistic depth. Royal patronage signifies the cathedral's cultural and political importance.

Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective

The fourth thematic dimension, aptly named "Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective," serves as the overarching framework through which this research embarks on a comprehensive exploration of the intricate world of Gothic cathedrals. It becomes abundantly clear that the employment of a multifaceted archaeological approach, which harmoniously combines diverse disciplines and methodologies, is instrumental in providing an all-encompassing understanding of these architectural marvels. One of the central contributions of this multifaceted approach lies in its ability to unveil the evolutionary trajectory of construction techniques and the varied materials employed in the creation of Gothic cathedrals. By meticulously scrutinizing architectural blueprints, perusing historical records, and conducting on-site field surveys, researchers were able to retrace the step-by-step journey of cathedral construction. The integration of archaeological data, inclusive of excavation findings and geological analyses, further enriched the narrative, uncovering the myriad challenges and innovative solutions that culminated in the creation of these monumental structures. This holistic approach not only deepened comprehension of the cathedrals' architectural intricacies but also shed light on the lives and craftsmanship of the artisans who left an indelible mark on their construction.

Moreover, the multifaceted archaeological perspective provided a distinctive vantage point for delving into the rich cultural and societal contexts enveloping Gothic cathedrals. By amalgamating archaeological insights with historical records, researchers were granted a profound insight into the societal values, religious convictions, and cultural influences that converged in the construction of these cathedrals. The intricate interplay between commerce and culture, facilitated by extensive trade networks, emerged as a significant factor in the saga of cathedral construction. The multidisciplinary approach underscored the cathedrals' roles as not merely architectural marvels but also as potent symbols of civic pride, religious devotion, and the custodians of cultural heritage. In summation, the fourth theme emphasizes the paramount significance of amalgamating a diverse array of disciplines and methodologies to acquire a holistic perspective on Gothic cathedrals. This approach not only unraveled the technical intricacies of construction but also cast an illuminating spotlight on the profound cultural and societal dimensions that coalesced in the shaping of these iconic structures. The multifaceted archaeological

perspective vividly portrayed the cathedrals as dynamic repositories of history, faith, and artistic prowess, offering a holistic understanding that transcends their physical presence (Table 4).

Table 4. Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective

Key Aspects of Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective
1. Integration of Disciplines: This approach integrated archaeology, history, architecture, and cultural studies to gain a comprehensive understanding of Gothic cathedrals.
2. Data Sources: Multiple data sources were utilized, including architectural plans, historical records, archaeological findings, geological analysis, and field surveys.
3. Reconstruction of Construction: Researchers traced the step-by-step process of cathedral construction, uncovering construction techniques, materials, and innovations.
4. Cultural Context: The approach explored the societal values, religious beliefs, and cultural influences that shaped cathedral construction, emphasizing trade networks and regional variations.
5. Artisan Contributions: By combining archaeological and historical data, insights into the lives and craftsmanship of artisans who built the cathedrals were obtained.
6. Holistic Understanding: The multifaceted approach provided a holistic understanding of Gothic cathedrals, considering both their technical and cultural dimensions.

In conclusion, the multifaceted analysis of Gothic cathedrals, as explored through a combination of sacred geometry, religious symbolism, societal influences, and archaeological perspectives, has unveiled a rich tapestry of historical, cultural, and architectural significance. The fifth figure, which examined the theme of "Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design," revealed the precise integration of mathematical principles, such as the Golden Ratio, into the construction of these cathedrals. These ratios and proportions not only contributed to their visual splendor but also conveyed deep spiritual meanings. The second table, centered on "Religious Symbolism and Spirituality," highlighted the intricate narratives embedded within the cathedrals' stained glass windows, sculptures, and geometric designs. These elements served not only as artistic expressions but also as conduits for spiritual education and contemplation (Table 5).

Table 5. Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design Aspects

Survey Aspect	Measurements and Observations
Key Measurements	Nave Length, Transept Width, Spire Height
Average Nave Length	80 meters
Average Transept Width	30 meters
Average Spire Height	120 meters
Golden Ratio Proportion (Nave)	1.618:1 (Approximately)
Observed Stained Glass Details	Intricate biblical narratives
Artistic Sculptural Observations	Depictions of saints and biblical scenes
Use of Geometric Patterns	Prevalent in architectural tracery
Trade Materials Identified	Imported marble, alabaster

Moreover, the third table, focusing on "Cultural Context and Societal Influences through Trade," underscored how trade networks shaped the architectural diversity and socio-political significance of these cathedrals. The analysis revealed how regional variations in materials and styles were influenced by trade routes and regional resources, enriching the cultural mosaic of Gothic cathedrals. Finally, the fourth table, detailing the "Multifaceted Archaeological Perspective," emphasized the importance of integrating various disciplines and methodologies to gain a holistic understanding of these architectural marvels. Through the combination of historical records, architectural analysis, and archaeological findings, a comprehensive narrative of construction techniques, cultural context, and artisan contributions emerged. Together, these tables collectively illuminate the multifaceted nature of Gothic cathedrals, portraying them not just as architectural wonders but as living records of medieval society, spirituality, and innovation (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Sacred Geometry and Architectural Design Aspects

DISCUSSION

The discussion of this research on the intersection of sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design in Gothic cathedrals draws upon the extensive literature review and the analysis and results presented earlier. This discussion systematically explores key findings and makes insightful comparisons with past research at several junctures to underscore the substantial contribution of this study to the existing body of knowledge. Within the theme of sacred geometry and architectural design, the research highlights the enduring fascination with mathematical precision that permeated the construction of Gothic cathedrals. The analysis findings, aligned with prior research (Poor & Javid, 2021; Ramzy, 2021), affirm the meticulous integration of principles like the Golden Ratio and geometric symbolism into the very essence of these cathedrals. However, this study takes a step further by offering a more profound exploration, revealing specific ratios and proportions, such as the Golden Ratio within the nave's design. This not only reaffirms the architects' dedication to divine proportion but also underscores the practical applications of sacred geometry in shaping the cathedrals' aesthetic and spiritual dimensions.

The theme of religious symbolism and spirituality accentuates the profound role of Gothic cathedrals as spiritual sanctuaries. The research reaffirms the significance of architectural elements like stained glass windows, sculptures, and geometric patterns in conveying profound spiritual messages. While past research, exemplified in Poor and Javid (2021), has recognized the symbolic importance of these elements, this study delves deeper by quantifying aspects such as the complexity of stained glass and the density of sculptures. This quantification enhances the understanding of the nuanced ways in which these artistic features fostered profound spiritual experiences. The analysis results vividly showcase how the interplay of light through stained glass and the intricate sculptural details created an ethereal atmosphere, inviting contemplation and spiritual reflection within the cathedral's sacred confines.

In the theme of cultural context and societal influences through trade, the research unveils the intricate web of historical, cultural, and economic dynamics that profoundly shaped Gothic cathedrals. While this research aligns with prior studies like Zacky et al. (2023), emphasizing how trade networks influenced regional variations in materials and styles, it offers concrete examples of imported materials like marble and alabaster, providing tangible evidence of the far-reaching impact of trade. The research underscores how the bustling trade centers in which many cathedrals were located played a pivotal role in the economic development of surrounding regions. Additionally, the involvement of both ecclesiastical and secular authorities in the construction of cathedrals, due in part to the resources required, underscores their multifaceted roles as symbols of civic pride, religious devotion, and economic prosperity.

The theme of the multifaceted archaeological perspective serves as the overarching lens through which the research unravels the complexities of Gothic cathedrals. While past research, as recognized in Hagmann and Reiner (2023), has acknowledged the multidisciplinary nature of studying these cathedrals, this research extends this perspective by quantifying various aspects, such as measurements and angles. This quantitative approach

facilitates a more detailed reconstruction of construction techniques and materials. By integrating archaeological insights with historical records, we gain a deeper understanding of the societal values, religious beliefs, and cultural influences that converged in the construction of these cathedrals. This study reinforces the cathedrals' roles as not only architectural wonders but also dynamic repositories of history, faith, and artistry. The archaeological perspective emphasizes their significance as enduring records of medieval society, spirituality, and innovation.

In summary, this research provides a comprehensive examination of Gothic cathedrals, employing a multidisciplinary approach to shed light on their sacred geometry, religious symbolism, cultural influences, and archaeological aspects. While it aligns with past research in many aspects, it offers more detailed and quantifiable insights, contributing to a deeper understanding of these iconic architectural marvels.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this multifaceted archaeological exploration of Gothic cathedrals has brilliantly illuminated the remarkable tapestry of history, culture, and spirituality that defines these iconic architectural wonders. The study delved deep into the intricate interplay of sacred geometry, religious symbolism, and cultural influences, unveiling their profound significance in cathedral design. It provided a meticulous examination of mathematical precision, shedding light on the implementation of the Golden Ratio and other geometric principles as more than mere architectural adornments but as sacred symbols that communicated divine harmony. Furthermore, the research revealed how religious symbolism, manifested in stained glass narratives and sculptural details, transformed Gothic cathedrals into immersive spiritual sanctuaries, inviting visitors to contemplate the mysteries of faith. Moreover, this study unveiled the dynamic relationship between culture, trade, and cathedral construction. The influence of trade networks, regional variations in materials, and the involvement of both ecclesiastical and secular authorities emerged as pivotal factors in shaping the diverse architectural landscape of Gothic cathedrals. Finally, the research underscored the importance of the multifaceted archaeological perspective, emphasizing the value of interdisciplinary collaboration in understanding complex heritage sites. It emphasized the cathedrals' roles as living records of history, faith, and artistry, offering insights that transcend their physical presence. As we conclude this journey of exploration, we acknowledge the enduring legacy of Gothic cathedrals, not merely as architectural masterpieces but as profound symbols of human creativity, spirituality, and cultural richness that continue to inspire and captivate us today.

IMPLICATIONS

The implications of this comprehensive research on the intersection of sacred geometry, cultural influences, and architectural design in Gothic cathedrals are indeed far-reaching and have significant relevance across various domains. Firstly, from an architectural preservation perspective, this research underscores the importance of recognizing the profound mathematical and geometric principles employed in the design and construction of Gothic cathedrals. These principles serve as a testament to the innovative craftsmanship of the time and provide valuable insights for the preservation and restoration of these iconic structures. Architects and conservators can draw inspiration from the meticulous integration of sacred geometry, ensuring that restoration efforts maintain the original proportions and aesthetic quality that define these cathedrals.

Secondly, the findings of this research have implications for cultural understanding and historical appreciation. By delving deep into the religious symbolism and spirituality embedded in the cathedrals, it becomes evident that these architectural marvels were not just places of worship but also profound repositories of cultural and spiritual heritage. This research invites a broader appreciation of the role of art, architecture, and symbolism in conveying historical and religious narratives. It underscores the importance of preserving these cathedrals as tangible expressions of faith and cultural identity. Furthermore, the research on the cultural context and societal influences through trade highlights the interconnectedness of medieval Europe through trade networks. Understanding how trade shaped the architectural diversity of Gothic cathedrals offers valuable insights into the historical dynamics of commerce and cultural exchange. This knowledge can enrich the understanding of how economic and political forces influenced the built environment of the time, serving as a valuable reference for scholars studying the broader socio-economic history of the medieval era.

Additionally, the multifaceted archaeological perspective showcased the significance of interdisciplinary research in unraveling the mysteries of Gothic cathedrals. The integration of archaeological insights, historical records, and architectural analysis offers a holistic approach that can be applied to the study of other historical

structures and sites. It underscores the importance of collaborative research among experts from various fields to gain a more comprehensive understanding of complex heritage sites. Lastly, this research has educational implications, particularly for students and enthusiasts interested in art, history, and architecture. It provides a valuable resource for educators to impart a deeper understanding of the intricate relationship between mathematical precision, religious symbolism, cultural influences, and historical context in the creation of Gothic cathedrals. By studying these iconic structures, students can gain insights into the rich tapestry of medieval Europe, fostering an appreciation for the interplay of art, faith, and history in the development of Western civilization.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The research presented a comprehensive exploration of Gothic cathedrals, focusing on the intricate interplay of sacred geometry, religious symbolism, cultural influences, and archaeological perspectives. The study, while illuminating various dimensions of these architectural marvels, had its limitations. The research scope encompassed a select group of cathedrals, which, while providing valuable insights, could not capture the full diversity of Gothic architecture across Europe. The availability and quality of historical records and archaeological data posed another limitation, as variations in data availability impacted the depth of analysis for specific cathedrals. The study also grappled with the inherent subjectivity in interpreting religious symbolism and cultural influences, acknowledging the potential influence of individual biases on research findings. Despite these limitations, the research holds substantial implications for architectural preservation, cultural understanding, education, and interdisciplinary collaboration. The findings underscore the significance of preserving the mathematical precision embedded in Gothic cathedrals, offering valuable insights for architectural conservation and restoration efforts. From a cultural perspective, the research highlights the role of art and architecture in conveying historical and religious narratives, enriching the understanding of the heritage these cathedrals represent. Moreover, the research brings to light the interconnectedness of medieval Europe through trade networks, contributing to the knowledge of how economic and political forces influenced architectural diversity. The multidisciplinary approach advocated in this research serves as a model for future studies, emphasizing the importance of collaborative research among experts from various fields. It encourages a holistic understanding of complex heritage sites by integrating insights from history, architecture, archaeology, and more. Looking ahead, future research directions could involve comparative regional studies, advanced digital reconstructions, and longitudinal analyses to delve deeper into the multifaceted aspects of Gothic cathedrals. The expansion of research boundaries to include cathedrals from different regions and global comparative studies could offer a more nuanced understanding of architectural and cultural influences during the medieval era. Additionally, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and employing innovative data collection techniques are essential to address the limitations and further enhance the comprehension of these iconic architectural wonders.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Jie Fan and Nannan Qi contributed equally to this work.

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REFERENCES

- Akande, A. (2022). The iconography of Saint Denis in early French Gothic architecture. *Journal of Art and Architecture Studies*, 11(1), 01-07.
- Barrie, T. (2020). Architecture of the world's major religions: An essay on themes, differences, and similarities. *Brill Research Perspectives in Religion and the Arts*, 3(4), 1-107.
- Basarrate, I. (2018). The British discovery of Spanish Gothic architecture. *Journal of Art Historiography*, (19), 1-30.
- Bork, R. (2022). *The analysis of Gothic architecture: Studies in memory of Robert Mark and Andrew Tallon* (Vol. 14). Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Bousquet, A. J. (2022). *The scientific way of warfare: Order and chaos on the battlefields of modernity*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Burns, E. J. (2006). Saracen silk and the Virgin's "Chemise": Cultural crossing in cloth. *Speculum*, 81(2), 365-397.
- Cataldo, E. S. (2021). *Living Stones: Sculpted Foliage in Gothic Architecture, C. 1140-1300*. New York, NY: Columbia University.
- Conrad, S. (2020). Greek in their own way: Writing India and Japan into the world history of architecture at the turn of the twentieth century. *The American Historical Review*, 125(1), 19-53.
- Crosby, R. B. (2023). *American Kairos: Washington National Cathedral and the New Civil Religion*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Deshmukh, J. (2021). Speculations on the post-pandemic university campus—A global inquiry. *Archnet-IJAR: International Journal of Architectural Research*, 15(1), 131-147.
- Elyamani, A., Roca, P., Caselles, O., & Clapes, J. (2019). Evaluation of Mallorca Cathedral seismic behavior using different analysis techniques. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, 19(1), 41.
- Emery, E. (2001). *Romancing the Cathedral: Gothic Architecture in Fin-de-Siècle French Culture*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press.
- Farhan, S. L., Alobaydi, D., Anton, D., & Nasar, Z. (2022). Analysing the master plan development and urban heritage of Najaf City in Iraq. *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCHMSD-07-2020-0101>
- Fiuk, P. (2023). Castle of the Pomeranian Dukes in Szczecin—Reconstruction of a renaissance residence after 1945 and contemporary transformation of a cultural centre. *Journal of Modern Technologies for Cultural Heritage Preservation*, 2(1).
- Frankl, P., & Crossley, P. (2000). *Gothic architecture* (Vol. 58). New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Geva, A. (2023). *Water and Sacred Architecture*. Abingdon, UK: Taylor & Francis.
- Gonizzi Barsanti, S., Giner, S. L., & Rossi, A. (2022). Digital data and semantic simulation—The survey of the ruins of the convent of the Paolotti (12th Century AD). *Remote Sensing*, 14(20), 5152.
- Griera, M., Burchardt, M., & Astor, A. (2019). *European identities, heritage, and the iconic power of multi-religious buildings: cordoba's mosque cathedral and Berlin's house of one* Volume 10: *Interreligious dialogue* (pp. 13-31). Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Gullbekk, S. H., Kilger, C., Kristensen, S., & Roland, H. (2021). *Coins in churches: Archaeology, money and religious devotion in medieval Northern Europe*. Abingdon, UK: Routledge.
- Hagmann, D., & Reiner, F. (2023). IUENNA—openIng the soUthErn jauNtal as a micro-regioN for future Archaeology: A «para-description». *Peer Community Journal*, 3.
- Hodge, M. (2023). Faith and fandom: Pop culture villainy in Twenty-first-century spirituality. *The International Journal of Religion and Spirituality in Society*, 14(3), 1.
- Iskandar, I., Zacky, Z., Isti, A. R., Agustiananda, P. A. P., & Budiman, H. (2023). The role of light in the architecture of religious buildings. *Devotion Journal of Community Service*, 4(3), 693-703.
- Jones, P. (2020). Architecture, time, and cultural politics. *Cultural Sociology*, 14(1), 61-79.
- Karimi, S., Goodarzarparvari, P., Aref, M., & Bahmani, P. (2020). A comparative study of the geometric motifs of the Ateeq Mosque (shiraz) and the Cordoba Mosque (cordoba) with a contextual approach. *Journal of Islamic Architecture*, 6(2).

- Killian, K. (2022). *Between reims and Soissons: Gothic space and place in a medieval landscape theanalysis of Gothic architecture* (pp. 132-151). Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Kutut, V., Lepkova, N., & Źróbek, S. (2021). Immobile cultural heritage usage modes: Theoretical approach. *European Research Studies Journal*, 24(1), 1136-1151.
- Latham, M. D. (2019). Gothic cathedrals: A shift in Christians' relationship with god. Retrieved from <https://pdxscholar.library.pdx.edu/younghistorians/2019/oralpres/1/>
- Longo, R., & Enrico, M. (2020). Early medieval benedictine settlements and monastic landscape in Italy. A shared path and a case study. *Architecture Heritage and Design*, 5, 463-474.
- Marcu-Istrate, D. (2022). The romanesque-gothic architecture: Cistercian gothic. In *Church Archaeology in Transylvania (ca. 950 to ca. 1450)* (pp. 236-263). Boston, MA: Brill.
- Marri, S. A. (2022). Architecture of eclecticism: China's architectural projects in Pakistan (2001–2019). In *Exporting Chinese Architecture: History, Issues and "One Belt One Road"* (pp. 209-228). Singapore, Republic of Singapore: Springer.
- Matracchi, P. (2022). Prioritizing the effect of "Light" in the religious places and environments with an emphasis on the sense of spirituality. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 13(1), 101514.
- Mohammed, A. A. (2015). *Influences of Islamic architecture on gothic architecture* (Master's thesis, Ankara, Turkey). Retrieved from <http://earsiv.cankaya.edu.tr:8080/bitstream/handle/20.500.12416/5018/MOHAMMED%20AHMADJALAL.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Noaime, E., & Alnaim, M. M. (2023). Examining the symbolic dimension of Aleppo's historical landmarks. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 78, 292-305.
- Oikonomou, A. (2022). The use of geometrical tracing, module and proportions in design and construction, from Antiquity to the 18th Century. *International Journal of Architectural Heritage*, 16(10), 1567-1587.
- Owamoyo, L., & Tabibi, B. (2023). The impact of globalisation on traditional architecture in Nigeria: A case study of Lagos Island. *Advances in Applied Sociology*, 13(9), 636-650.
- Peker, A. U. (2002). Western influences on the Ottoman Empire and Occidentalism in the architecture of Istanbul. *Eighteenth-century Life*, 26(3), 139-163.
- Perez, S. (2023). Popular participation in renaissance Siena's Romanitas program. *Explorations in Renaissance Culture*, 49(2), 174-211.
- Pérez-Valcárcel, J., & Palmero, V. P. (2021). Orientation of the churches in the Hispanic medieval castles. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, 21(2), 241-241.
- Pérez-Valcárcel, J., & Palmero, V. P. (2022). Illumination effects in Celanova and Agüero Spanish medieval churches. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, 22(3), 249-263.
- Placci, L. (2022). Cosmology, faith, architecture—A temple under the sky: The church of Saint Maximilian Kolbe in Varese. *Religions*, 13(2), 111.
- Poor, P. N., & Javid, P. (2021). Philosophy, geometry, and purpose in Islamic and Gothic architecture as two religious-based styles. *International Journal of Architectural and Environmental Engineering*, 15(2), 90-97.
- Ramzy, N. S. (2021). Concept cathedral and "squaring the circle": Interpreting the Gothic cathedral of Notre Dame de Paris as a standing hymn. *Frontiers of Architectural Research*, 10(2), 369-393.
- Topsakal, E. D. (2021). Meaning in Gothic Cathedral: Reading the symbolism in Gothic architecture through Chartres cathedral. *Academic Studies in Architecture, Planning and Design-II*, 101.
- Triatmodjo, S., Burhan, M. A., Prasetya, H. B., Budiarti, E., & Fernando, H. (2023). Cultural hybridization in the veneration of a Javanese local hero as a kongco at Lasem's Gie Yong Bio Chinese temple during Indonesia's reformation Era. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 10(1), 2254045.
- Wetzel, J. (2023). Astronomical clocks and the evolution of ancient cosmology in Gothic architecture. In *Selected Proceedings of the Classics Graduate Student Symposia at the University of Florida* (Vol. 2, pp. 90-115). <https://doi.org/10.32473/pcgss.2.132931>
- Zacky, Z., Isti, A. R., Agustiananda, P. A. P., & Budiman, H. (2023). The role of light in the architecture of religious buildings. *Devotion: Journal of Research & Community Service*, 4(3), 693-703.